

7.1 Country Brief: A social psychological perspective on trends of extremism in Georgia

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Georgian Institute of Politics

About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and broader social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) to move towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalisation programmes. We intend to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, including a sense of being victimised, being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts, including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and de-radicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of seventeen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation-states adapt to new security challenges. Mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts is crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that radicalisation processes often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national justice frameworks. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation is central to the project’s aims.

Executive Summary

This country brief summarises the survey findings for Georgia. It then embeds the survey findings within a national and cultural context for each country. The aim of these summaries is to situate the findings within their respective sociopolitical and sociocultural contexts. The literature review and rationale for the proposed model, analysis of the full dataset, and discussion can be found in the full 7.1 report, which also contains the country briefs.

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1. Results

Georgia had 38.57% of participants reporting that they did not know their political attitudes. Thus, this variable was removed from the model, and these participants were kept, resulting in a sample of $n = 140$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
Mean age (SD)	n	%	n	%	n	%
22.62 (3.36)	62	44.28	78	55.71	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	106	75.71
Agnostic/Atheist	28	20.00
Other	6	4.29
Jewish	0	0.00
Muslim	0	0.00
Buddhist	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	25	17.86
No	99	70.71
Don't know	16	11.43

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Gender	17	68.00
Sexuality	11	44.00
Other	4	16.00
Colour or race	1	4.00
Age	1	4.00

Disability	1	4.00
Nationality	0	0.00
Religion	0	0.00
Language	0	0.00
Ethnic group	0	0.00

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	9	6.43	51	36.43	79	56.43	1	0.71
Sport or recreational organization	13	9.29	34	24.29	93	66.43	0	0.00
Art, music or educational organization	46	32.86	36	25.71	57	40.71	1	0.71
Labour union	5	3.57	18	12.86	117	83.57	0	0.00
Political party	4	2.86	14	10.00	122	87.14	0	0.00
Environmental organization	11	7.86	28	20.00	101	72.14	0	0.00
Professional association	13	9.29	19	13.57	108	77.14	0	0.00
Humanitarian or charitable organization	20	14.29	21	15.00	98	70.00	1	0.71
Consumer organization	13	9.29	15	10.71	109	77.86	3	2.14
Self-help group or mutual help group	23	16.43	15	10.71	101	72.14	1	0.71
Women's group	15	10.71	25	17.86	99	70.71	1	0.71
Other organization	9	6.43	13	9.29	98	70.00	20	14.29

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	19	13.57	110	78.57	11	7.86
Worked in a political party or action group	10	7.14	124	88.57	6	4.29
Worked in another ideological organization	11	7.86	122	87.14	7	5.00
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	23	16.43	109	77.86	8	5.71
Signed a petition	78	55.71	58	41.43	4	2.86
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	67	47.86	67	47.86	6	4.29
Boycotted certain products	58	41.43	74	52.86	8	5.71
Posted or shared anything about politics online	67	47.86	62	44.29	11	7.86

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was linked with increased perceptions of migrants as a threat to one's national ingroup regarding access to welfare, resources, and power. Additionally, perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was also linked to increased perceived realistic threat from migrants. Greater feelings of anomie were also associated with perceiving migrants as a greater threat.

Direct predictors of extremism

In turn, perceiving that migrants were a greater threat to one's national ingroup was associated with greater endorsement of extremist attitudes. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing greater social alienation was also associated with more support for extremism.

Indirect predictors on extremism

The Georgian participant sample was the smallest across our national contexts (please note that the Georgian sample is the only sample which was not collected via Qualtrics, but instead through a local university); this may account for the lack of reported indirect effects, rather than their absence due to meaningful differences with other samples. Increased social dominance orientation had a significant indirect effect on increased support for extremist attitudes via increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat. The total indirect effect of social dominance orientation was not significant.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Endorsing more right-wing and populist attitudes were both separately associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia and Russian culture.

None of the variables of interest (i.e. social dominance orientation, online group identity, collective narcissism, anomie, individual and group relative deprivation, social cohesion, social alienation, populism, political trust, perceptions of migrants as realistic threats, support for extremist attitudes) reliably predicted attitudes towards either Ukrainian or Russian migrants.

Figure 7. Respecified model for Georgia.

2. Situating the findings within the Georgian context

This report aims to examine and interpret D.Rad survey findings for Georgia. It is important to note that radicalisation trends in Georgia need to be situated within the context of ultraconservative discourse coming from the Georgian Orthodox Church – the most trusted and popular institution in the country, with 91% of Georgians having a favourable attitude towards the Patriarch (IRI 2023, 28). It is even more noteworthy that as Georgia enters the parliamentary elections cycle scheduled for 2024, the current ruling party, Georgian Dream (GD), has also turned to radical, illiberal and ultraconservative discourse. Prime Minister Irakli Gharibashvili even attended the Conservative Political Action Conference (CPAC) in Hungary in May of 2023, leading to the Party of European Socialists (PES) condemning and even suspending GD's observer member status (PES 2023).

With the Georgian Dream trying to secure power for the fourth time in 2024, political discourse will more likely become even more polarised with the dividing lines between “traditional values” and “liberalism”. These discourses are also very much embedded in Christianity as D.Rad survey also illustrates that more than 75% of the respondents identify as Christians. Orthodox Christianity serves as an important marker for national identity discourse in Georgia, especially those narratives that are ethnic-based and exclusionary.

The survey shows that despite the average age of the participants being only 22.62, the number of those who identify themselves as religious, and specifically as Christians, is relatively high – 75,71%. In comparison, some studies show that most youth in most European countries do not identify with any religion (Sherwood 2018). This suggests that Orthodox Christianity is still very relevant and plays an important role in the radicalisation processes in Georgia. Yet, it also needs to be noted that while respondents identify as Christians, active membership in the Church is only 6.43%. This shows that social and mass media are more important factors in radicalisation than institutions and attendance of sermons.

The Survey also offers interesting information regarding trust in political parties, government and state institutions. More specifically, data shows that very few in the last 12 months contacted a politician or government official, worked in a political party or action group, worked in another ideological organisation, or displayed a campaign badge/sticker. This is in accordance with larger datasets that show that trust in political parties and state institutions in Georgia remains extremely low (IRI 2023). On the other hand, the D.Rad survey shows that those who have posted something about politics online, boycotted some product, or attended a lawful protest are higher (a bit below half of the respondents), suggesting that it is not so much that young people do not care about issues but it is that they do not feel represented or that state institutions/politicians care about them. And this divide between the people and politicians could push youth towards more radicalisation.

Regarding attitudes toward Russian immigrants, such an increase in right-wing political attitudes and for extreme measures (e.g., “We should break all cooperation with Russian academics, artists, and athletes.”) could be explained by the ontological insecurity of

Georgians. To be more exact, as Georgia remains outside NATO and the EU security umbrella and is technically still at war with Russia since the latter keeps violating the cease-fire agreement and occupying Georgian territories, Georgians worry about the Russian influx. Georgia has been one of the main escape points for Russians feeling the war, with various estimates of more than 100,000 Russians currently in Georgia, having a population of barely 4 million (Reuters, 2023). The sudden influx of immigrants has led to inflation, a housing market crisis, and more widespread use of the Russian language than there was before. On top of it, the Georgian government has not introduced any restrictions or visa-related regulations, which has increased fear among many Georgians even further. The low trust in state institutions creates a feeling in the population that they have to take matters into their own hands, hence the increase of right-wing political attitudes in the survey.

The survey also showed that discrimination based on race, age, nationality or disability is not so common in Georgia, while gender and sexuality-based discrimination is more prevalent. This again could be explained because of the conservative discourse that is coming from some of the higher hierarchs of the Georgian Orthodox Church and government officials, and that is borderline homophobia and transphobia.

We can draw a few conclusions. First, Orthodox Christianity remains a dominant discourse in the country, serving as a critical feature of Georgia's national identity. This, time and again, encourages radical groups to mobilise the masses and harness their popular power to resort to verbal or even physical violence, mainly against sexual minorities. Second, there is widespread alienation from the political class and the policy-making process within the population, including young people. The feelings of being excluded and disenfranchised may push many young people into a radicalised corner. Third, Georgia is in a vulnerable geopolitical position, exposed to various global risks. The Russian invasion of Ukraine and the times of "Zeitenwende" have further exacerbated the severity or perception of the severity of these risks, such as the influx of Russian migrants, leading to feelings of ontological insecurity among the local population. Coupled with rising living costs and other socio-economic challenges, this may lead to radicalisation and further alienation from the normal political processes for disadvantaged groups in the population.

3. References

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